

Synthesis of *cis*- α -Bisabolene

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The nitrile, 3-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)but-2-enylcyanide (3) was procured by the reaction of cuprous cyanide in DMSO on 3-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)but-2-enyl bromide (2). On alcoholysis, the above cyanide furnished methyl 4-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)pent-3-enoate (4) which was smoothly reduced to the corresponding carbinol (5). The key intermediate, 4-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)pent-3-en-1-al (6) was prepared by the oxidation of the carbinol (5) with CrO_3/Py which upon Wittig reaction with isopropylidene triphenylphosphorane gave *cis*- α -bisabolene.

CIS- α -Bisabolene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon isomeric with β -, γ - and iso-bisabolene, occurs widely in nature, e.g. *Hymeraea corbarie* resin¹ and other essential oils²⁻⁴. Literature⁵ records a synthesis of the title compound. We wish to report a new and facile synthesis of this hydrocarbon (1) which is schematically depicted below.

The starting material, 3-(4'-methylcyclohex-1-3'-en-1-yl)but-2-enylbromide⁶ (2), on its reaction with cuprous cyanide in dimethylsulphoxide⁶ furnished 3-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)but-2-enyl cyanide (3) which on alcoholysis⁶ provided the corresponding methyl ester (4) in 80% yield. Methyl 4-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)pent-3-enoate (4) was smoothly reduced with lithium aluminium hydride in dry

ether to give the alcohol (5) in 70% yield, which was subsequently oxidised. [with Collins reagent⁷ to afford the corresponding aldehyde (6) in 68% yield. This aldehyde was submitted to Wittig reaction⁸ with isopropylidene triphenyl phosphonium iodide in dimethylsulphoxide in the presence of sodium hydride to yield the hydrocarbon (1). The latter was purified through column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as eluent followed by distillation under reduced pressure. Spectral analysis (ir and pmr) of 1 had comparable bands with those reported for naturally occurring *cis*- α -bisabolene.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (films) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectro-

photometer having sodium chloride optics. Nmr spectra (60 MHz) were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

3-(4'-Methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)but-2-enyl cyanide (3): A solution of 3-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)but-2-enyl bromide (2; 12.4 g) in dimethylsulphoxide (25 ml) was added dropwise over 20 min to a well stirred suspension of cuprous cyanide (11.3 g) in DMSO (100 ml) and stirred for 1 h at rate, at 40° for 1 h and at 85° for 2 h. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water (50 ml) and extracted with ether. The organic phase was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation yielded 3 (6.6 g, 70%), b.p. 125–30°/7 mm (Found: C, 81.94; H, 9.81; N, 8.35. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$ requires: C, 82.28; H, 9.72; N, 8.03%); η_D^{25} 1.4953; ν_{max} 2 240 (CN), 840 and 810 cm^{-1} .

Methyl 4-(4'-methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)pent-3-enoate (4): A slow stream of hydrogen chloride gas was bubbled into a solution of 3 (13.75 g) in methanol (40 ml) and water (3 ml). The resulting heat of reaction caused the solvent to reflux. After the temperature had subsided (15 min), the reaction mixture was treated with water (8 ml), warmed on a steam-bath for 20 min and poured into an excess of cold water. The solution was extracted with ether, washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and brine, and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was expelled and the residue was distilled under vacuum to furnish 4 (13.1 g, 80%), b.p. 115–20°/10 mm (Found: C, 74.79; H, 9.53. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 75.05; H, 9.62%); η_D^{25} 1.4975; ν_{max} 1 740 (ester), 840 and 805 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

4-(4'-Methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)pent-3-enol (5): To a fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.75 g) in dry ether (200 ml) was added dropwise, with stirring, the ester 4 (12 g) in anhydrous ether (50 ml) so as to keep ether at a gentle reflux. After stirring the reaction mixture for another 3 h, it was cooled and poured into ice-cold saturated solution

of sodium potassium tartrate, extracted with ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and subsequent distillation under vacuum afforded the carbinol **5** (7.2 g, 70%), b.p. 120–25°/10 mm (Found: C, 79.65; H, 11.03. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires: C, 80.00; H, 11.11%); η_D^{25} 1.5035; ν_{max} 3 400, 1 050 (OH), 840 and 180 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

4-(4'-Methylcyclohex-3'-en-1-yl)pent-3-en-1-al (**6**): Chromium trioxide (15.0 g) was added in small instalments to a well cooled solution of anhydrous pyridine (24 ml) and methylene chloride (80 ml) with stirring. The contents were stirred for further 15 min at room temperature. To it, a solution of the alcohol **5** (4.5 g) in methylene chloride (15 ml) was added in one portion. A tarry black deposit separated out immediately. After stirring for additional 15 min at room temperature, the solution was decanted and the residue extracted with methylene chloride (10 ml). The combined organic extract was washed with saturated brine solution and dried. The residue, left after the removal of the solvent, was subsequently distilled under vacuum to give the pure aldehyde **6** (3 g, 68%), b.p. 110–15°/10 mm (Found: C, 80.78; H, 9.85. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires: C, 80.90; H, 10.11%); η_D^{25} 1.4975; ν_{max} 2 720, 1 710 (C=O), 845 and 815 cm^{-1} (triply substituted double bond).

cis- α -Bisabolene (**1**): Isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane was prepared under the atmosphere of nitrogen from sodium hydride (0.54 g, 50%) in dimethylsulphoxide (6 ml) and isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (4.85 g) in dimethylsulphoxide

(12 ml) as usual. To it was added the aldehyde **6** (2 g) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) at room temperature with constant stirring. A deep red colour appeared, and the contents were further stirred for 2 h and warmed for 0.5 h at 50° and left overnight at room temperature. The material was decomposed with cold water and the organic compound was taken up in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by chromatography over neutral alumina and elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (50 ml) afforded the hydrocarbon (**1**). It was further purified by distillation at 98–100°/4 mm to give **1** (1.352 g, 59%) (Found: C, 87.96; H, 11.50. Requires: C, 88.16; H, 11.84%); η_D^{25} 1.4865; ν_{max} 2 950, 1 640, 1 450, 1 375, 1 150, 1 025, 980, 965, 915, 885, 870, 810, 800, 750, 725 and 700 cm^{-1} .

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